

Additional file 7: Figure S7. Endogenous rat total and S129 phosphorylated levels. Fresh frozen striatal and ventral midbrain tissue samples of naïve rats were sequentially lysed in first 1% Triton (A) then in 1% SDS containing lysis buffer (B) and diluted 1:300 or 1:10, respectively. Samples (n=6 per region) were run on AlphaLISA uniplex assays using the biotinylated syn-1 antibody (BD Biosciences, UK) combined with either 4D6 (Abcam, UK) or 11A5 (Prothena Biosciences Inc.) conjugated on the Europium Acceptor-beads for the detection of total and pS129 asyn, respectively. As reference protein, pS129 h-Asyn was used for both assays and spiked into appropriate asyn knockout mouse brain lysate. Total (open) and pS129 (filled) r-Asyn levels are presented in overlapping bars. Numbers inside the bars show the percent of pS129 to total r-Asyn. Error bars indicate SEM.